

A Proposed Model for Translating Proverbs and Sayings; A Case of Lying Proverbs and Sayings

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Abstract

This study proposed a model for translating proverbs and sayings from English into Arabic and vice versa. The model is based on translation as a process and product. It consists of three steps: understanding, transfer, and assessment. Each step has certain points to fulfil. It was validated by a group of jurors specializing in translation, curriculum and instruction. The model was modified based on the jurors' opinions. Then the model was applied to lying proverbs and sayings. The application came up with four kinds of translations: literal, semantic, idiomatic, and colloquial. It is recommended to apply the model to other types of proverbs and sayings.

Keywords: Proverbs, Sayings, Translation, Model

• Introduction

Reading the proverbs and sayings of other cultures is an interesting way to gain insight into life that your own culture might not have. Not only that, you can see how much philosophy is shared between cultures, and how common sayings in your culture manifest in others, and vice versa. Arabic culture in particular has a long, rich history, and it shows in their countless proverbs.

No one would deny that lying is a bad habit. Truth and lies are at the core of all our relationships: parents and children, wives and husbands, employers and employees, and law enforcement officials and criminals (Soorjoo, 2009). Motive also matters to the liar. A person who believes they have a moral justification for their lie, will find it easier to deceive a truth seeker. A person who stands to lose much if their lie is exposed, has a greater incentive to successfully lie, but will experience greater pressure at the same time which may 'leak' out in their verbal or nonverbal communication.

People start lying when they are children. It sometimes helps us get what we want. Sometimes it gets us in trouble. Most of us learn that, generally speaking, lying is not a good thing and we tell the truth most of the time. However, some people develop the belief that lying helps us get more of what we want. Therefore, they do it all time. Lying becomes something done naturally for them. Lies are statements intended to mislead others.

• Importance of Proverbs

Proverbs are considered a record of human existence, exhibiting all forms of life. They give a deep insight into domestic life, and open for us the heart of man. They have not ceased to be the treasuries of thought. Furthermore, Mieder (2004) asserts that proverbs are the most concise form of language. They fulfill the human need to summarize experiences and observations into nuggets of wisdom that provide ready-made comments. On the other hand, proverbs have not lost their usefulness in modern society. They serve people well in oral speech and the written word, coming to mind almost automatically when the situation requires them. They are regarded as significant rhetorical force in various modes of communication, from friendly chats, powerful political speeches, and religious sermons to lyrical poetry, best-seller novels, and influential mass media. Proverbs are in fact everywhere.

• Definition

Definitions of the proverb vary due to the writer's perspective of the proverb. Norrick (1985, 78) proposed the following definition for the proverb in terms of a genre: "a traditional, conversational, didactic genre with general meaning, a potential free conversational turn, preferably with figurative meaning." Mollanazar (2001, 53) defined it

as "a unit of meaning in a specific context through which the speaker and hearer arrive at the same meaning." Meider (2004, 119) defined it as "a short, generally known sentence of the folk which contains wisdom, truth, morals, and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed, and memorable form and which is handed down from generation to generation." Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (2015) defined it as "a short well-known statement that gives advice or expresses something that is generally true."

On the other, an *adage* is a *proverb* or a short statement expressing a general truth. Efforts are made to draw a distinction between a proverb and an adage, but in common usage, the words are interchangeable. There may be a sense that an adage is a classier word than a proverb. Because a saying becomes a proverb or an adage by being repeated from generation to generation, the expression an "old adage" is often criticized for being redundant, but it is widespread (Maddox, 2014).

Based on these definitions of the proverb, certain characteristics of it can be inferred as follows; it is not necessary that each proverb has all these characteristics:

- **Proverbs are self-contained:** none of their essential grammatical units may be replaced. Norrick (1985) argues that this characteristic distinguishes proverbs from proverbial phrases, like "*to face the music*" and "*Brown as a berry*" that are immediately excluded from the class of proverbs because they lack precisely essential grammatical units, which can thus be substituted into them at will.
- **Proverbs are (propositional) statement:** they are full statements.
- **Proverbs are (grammatical) sentences:** they must be complete (or elliptical, i.e., *Once bitten, twice shy*) sentences.
- **Proverbs are related to traditions:** the traditional nature of proverbs correlates closely with their status as items of folkloric.
- **Shortness (Brevity):** it must be succinct, utterable in a breath. Brevity, "the soul of wit", will be eminently the soul of a proverb's wit: the fewest possible words to convey this wisdom.
- **Sense:** Dabaghi et al. (2010) state that the sense is sometimes sacrificed by alliteration, in certain cases, such as *Forgive and forget*.
- **Salt:** Dabaghi et al (2010) assert that a proverb must have salt, that is, besides its good sense, it must in its manner and outward form be pointed, having a sting, which will make it memorable.

Arora (1995) provides the following characteristics:

- **Parallelism:** it shows parallelism, for example, *Show me a liar and I will show you a thief.*
- **Rhyme:** it is rhymed, for instance, *When the cat is away, the mice will play* (Arora,1995).
- **Hyperbole:** it contains exaggeration, i.e., *All is fair in love and war* (Arora,1995).
- **Paradox:** it presents a paradox, like *For there to be peace there must first be war* (Arora,1995).

Honeck (1997) adds the following characteristics:

- **Synecdoche:** it contains synecdoche (the literal meaning is quite different from the figurative meaning), such as *The early bird catches the worm*
- **Metaphor:** it shows a metaphoric meaning; a nominal symbolizes some characteristic attribute, for example, *Fair play is a jewel.*
- **Metonymy:** it involves a metonymic meaning; the association between something literally named and the thing intended, for instance, *who has a fair wife, needs more than two eyes* in which the eye stands metonymically for the sight.
- **Hyperbole:** it contains hyperbolic meaning; hyperbole counts as amplification; amplification says more than necessary. *Faint heart never won fair lady* is a hyperbolic proverb due to the existence of never in it.
- **Paradox:** it entails a logical contradiction. *A man's house is heaven and hell as well* is a paradoxical proverb.

• The Origin of Proverbs

The origin of the proverb is essential for understanding it well. The origin of most proverbs is unknown, but Meider (2004) argues that proverbs do not fall out of the sky. Instead, they are always coined by an individual either intentionally or unintentionally: a proverb is the wit of one and the wisdom of many. He also explains how a statement can turn into a proverb. He believes that if the statement contains an element of truth or wisdom, and if it exhibits one or more proverbial markers, it might “catch on” and be used first in a small family circle, and subsequently in a village, a city, a region, a country, a continent, and eventually the world. He concedes that it is usually quite difficult to trace the origin of a proverb in a particular language.

- **Lying proverbs and sayings**

The importance of lying proverbs and sayings is undeniable as our relationships with others are based on two opposite concepts: truth and lying. Hence, it is crucial to know the wisdom behind lying proverbs and sayings in different cultures, languages, and times. Moreover, it is essential to know the divisions of lying, and lying with children. Most importantly, the concept of lying needs some clarification as it is not always the deliberate act of deviating from the truth. In Islamic Sharia, lying is violating Sharia. It is vital to know whether lying is permissible or not.

- **Arabic Proverbs**

Some Arabic proverbs are adopted from the Quran. While some Arabic proverbs are formal or literary, the majority are informal and their pronunciation is colloquial. Some Arabic and English proverbs are similar such as:

الكذب مالوش رجلين (الكذب ليس له رجلين)

Literal: *lying has no legs*.

Idiomatic: A lie has no legs (but a scandal has wings).¹

- **Previous Studies**

Translating proverbs poses a lot of problems for the translator; because each proverb conveys a specific meaning in a specific context of situation. Therefore, a proverb should be rendered with care to carry the same cultural effect of the original proverb. It is not reasonable to translate a proverb while just looking at the first meaning of its words in a dictionary. Literal word-for-word translation does not work for proverbs. To properly translate a proverb requires several steps, and it often requires a translator to delve deeper into the culture of the source and target languages to determine the idiomatic translation. Baker (1992) proposed four strategies for the translation of proverbs as follows:

1. Using a proverb of similar meaning and form of SL one.
2. Using a proverb of similar meaning but dissimilar form of SL idiom.
3. Translation by paraphrase
4. Translation by omission

Gorjian (2008) proposed a model for translating proverbs consisting of three translation strategies in the form of three versions: (1) a weak version through which the translator focuses on adaptive or explained equivalent in the TL, (2) a moderate version through which the translator deals with a close equivalent in the TL, and (3) a strong version which focuses on the exact equivalent or the one which is one-to-one correspondence to the translated equivalent in the TL. The three-dimensional model of

¹ <https://www.yourdictionary.com/a-lie-has-no-legs>

translation works based on a three-fold strategy. This strategy may help the translator focuses on the hierarchical strategies through which the translator starts from the first strategy (exact equivalents - strong version) and if there are not any exact equivalents, he/she shifts to the second strategy (i.e., near equivalents - moderate version); and again if there are not any near equivalents, the translator tries to comprehend and interpret the message of the proverb and render the proverb message in to TL literally (weak version).

Mollanazar (2001) argued that proverbs cannot be translated literally and they may sometimes have no natural figurative equivalents in TL. Thus, he proposed two strategies in translating proverbs:

- a) Some similar proverbs can be found in the two languages with more or less similar forms, vocabulary and meaning and;
- b) Many proverbs may be found in the two languages which have similar meanings and can be applied in the same context, but they have different forms and vocabulary.

Beekman and Callow (1974) proposed three techniques to translate a proverb as follows:

1. The words following the proverb could be introduced as the meaning of the proverb.
2. It can be replaced with an equivalent local proverb.
3. Its non-figurative meaning could be stated straight forwardly.

Putri (2011) sought to study the students' translation of proverbs. This qualitative research used the descriptive method to achieve its purpose. The source of data is twenty respondents selected from the sixth semester English Department students. In collecting research data, an open and closed questionnaire was used. The questionnaire result aimed to find out the kinds of methods and strategies used by students in translating proverbs. The findings were related to 1) the kinds of translation methods that the students used in translating proverbs are free translation (41%), literal translation (20%), adaptation (17%), communicative translation (12%), idiomatic translation (5%), semantic translation (2%), faithful translation (2%), and word-for-word translation (1%); and 2) the kinds of translation strategies that the students used in translating proverbs are translation by paraphrase (43%), translation by omission (24%), using a proverb of similar meaning and form of the SL one (19%), and using a proverb of similar meaning but dissimilar form of the SL proverb (14%). In this research, it is concluded that in the translation of proverbs: 1) the method that most widely used by the students is free translation and the least method used by the students is word-for-word translation, and then 2) the strategy that mostly used by students is translation by paraphrase and the least strategy used by the students is using a proverb of similar meaning but dissimilar form of the SL proverb.

Deweik and Thalji (2015) explored the obstacles that Jordanian novice translators encounter when translating proverbs. They examined the strategies they use when

translating proverbs from Arabic into English and vice versa. 20 Jordanian novice translators were selected. The researchers designed a translation test that consisted of 10 Arabic proverbs and another 10 English proverbs based on Speake's (2008) categorization of proverbs. The translators were asked to translate the Arabic ones into English and the English ones into Arabic. The proverbs covered many themes. The researchers also conducted open-ended interviews with four academic and professional translators to obtain more information about the obstacles, causes, and strategies of translating proverbs. The study revealed that the obstacles which Jordanian novice translators face when translating proverbs from Arabic into English and vice versa are: inability to translate culturally bound words/ expressions properly; giving wrong TL equivalents, irrelevant meaning and wrong paraphrasing; using literal translation and misuse of appropriate lexical words; committing linguistic, stylistic, and grammatical mistakes; and unfamiliarity with translation strategies and techniques. Moreover, the strategies they used while translating proverbs were: rendering TL equivalent, which accounted for 181 instances, 45.25% of the total responses; the paraphrase technique, which accounted for 88 instances 22%; literal translation which reached to 57 instances 14.25%; and glossing which accounted for three instances 0.75% of the total translation. The study recommends investigating the structure and style of English proverbs in comparison with Arabic.

Based on the previous studies and attempts to translate proverbs, it is clear that a lot of efforts were exerted to tackle their translation. All these efforts indicate the difficulties surrounding translating proverbs. These studies did not say something about understanding proverbs as an important step of translating proverbs. Additionally, they did not speak about tracing the origin of the proverbs as an essential step towards understanding them. Assessment is a vital step missing in these studies. Hence, the researcher proposes a model that takes these steps into consideration when translating proverbs so as to produce acceptable translations of proverbs.

- **Statement of Problem**

Translating proverbs poses a lot of problems due to their cultural, semantic, syntactic, and stylistic connotations.

- **Question of the study**

This study tries to answer the following question:

How to offer a comprehensive model for translating proverbs?

- **Purpose of the Study**

This study attempts to find a comprehensive mode for translating proverbs.

- **Significance of the study**

This study gains its significance from:

- Proposing a comprehensive model for translating proverbs.
- Applying the model to lying proverbs in English and Arabic.

- **Delimitations of the Study**

This study is limited to lying proverbs.

- **Instrument of the study**

A jury members' evaluation sheet was presented to a group of specialists in translation, and curriculum and instruction to validate the model (*See Appendix 1*). The jury consisted of 15 members. They offered some remarks and modifications which the researcher took into consideration.

- **Data collection**

Proverbs and sayings about lying are collected from different sources, such as books and websites.

- **Procedures**

- Reviewing the literature related to proverbs and translating proverbs to provide the theoretical background of the study.
- Preparing the model for translating proverbs
- Presenting the proposed model to jury members for validation
- Taking the jury's remarks into consideration
- Applying the model to lying proverbs in English and Arabic.
- Reporting conclusions
- Suggesting recommendations

- **The Proposed Model**

The present study proposes a model of translating proverbs, Figure 1 taking the case of lying proverbs. The model is based on translation as a process and as a product. The model consists of three steps: understanding, transfer, and assessment. Each step has certain points to fulfil. The understanding step starts with reading, tracing the origin of the proverb and specifying its characteristics. The transfer step beings with taking into account the characteristics of the proverb as much as possible; producing an idiomatic proverb as much as possible: carrying the communicative effect; and producing a communicative meaning

as much as possible. The final step of the assessment ascertains the quality of the translation of the proverb.

Understanding	
1. Reading	To read the proverb to make sense of it.
2. Tracing the origin	The origin of the proverb gives clues about its meaning
3. Specifying Characteristics	Determining the characteristics help formulating the proverb in the target language
Transfer	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taking into Account the characteristics of the proverb as much as possible. - Producing an idiomatic proverb as much as possible: carrying the communicative effect - Producing a communicative or semantic meaning as much as possible 	
Assessment	
Using assessment criteria help achieve translation quality.	

Figure 1: A Model of Translating Proverbs

Following is a description of the model in some detail:

○ **Understanding**

The first step of translating a proverb is to understand its meaning properly. Therefore, the translator has to read the proverb carefully to get the right meaning because when we read a proverb for the first time, we probably get a wrong meaning. It often helps to determine the origin of the proverb, especially if it is not an entirely common saying: in what situation, under what conditions, etc. is the proverb used in the source and target languages, as well as what was the original version of the proverb, if it has been transformed over time. An obscure literary proverb should not be translated into a very familiar proverb in the target language. It is best to aim for equivalence between the proverb's standing within the context of the source culture and the target.

○ **Transfer**

Often, proverbs deal directly with societal customs that might not translate directly to certain other societies. In these cases, it might help to find a saying that approximates the intended message of the proverb and this equals to an idiomatic translation. When we cannot find a similar proverb in the target language, it is better to aim for a communicative meaning. In both cases, idiomatic translation and communicative translation, it is important to pay attention to the proverb characteristic in the source and target languages.

○ Assessment

Proverb translation assessment plays an important role in producing an accurate and acceptable translation. Hence, the process of translating a proverb does not end with the transfer of meaning, yet a crucial step is essential: assessment. There should be some criteria for assessing the translation of a proverb, such as:

- Does the translation give a similar proverb in the target language?
- Does the translation give a communicative meaning?
- Does the translation bring about the communicative effect of the proverb in the source language?
- Does the translation have the characteristics of the proverb in the source language?
- Is it free from any linguistic errors?
- Is it as concise as the original?
- Is the connotative meaning shared by both the target and source languages?

Therefore, translating proverbs may fall within four strategies:

- **Idiomatic (Communicative) translation:** this is the most appropriate strategy. It focuses on the message.
- **Semantic translation:** this is an appropriate strategy as long as there is no idiomatic translation. It focuses on the meaning.
- **Literal translation:** it is of two kinds, either acceptable or unacceptable.
- **Colloquial translation:** especially in proverbs, it can work well as long as it carries the meaning well.

These four strategies will be applied to the translation of proverbs and sayings.

● An Application of the Model

The following is an application of the suggested model for translating proverbs. First, the proverb is presented followed by variants of the proverb. Finally, translation of the proverb is offered. 60 proverbs and sayings are translated: 30 from English into Arabic (10 translated literally, 10 translated semantically, and 10 translated idiomatically); 30 from Arabic into English (10 translated literally, 10 translated semantically and 10 translated idiomatically).

A. From English into Arabic

1. **Above all, don't lie to yourself. The man who lies to himself and listens to his own lie comes to a point that he cannot distinguish the truth within him, or around him, and so loses all respect for himself and for others. And having no respect he ceases to love.**" (Fyodor Dostoyevsky).²

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

في معظم الأحوال، لا تكذب على نفسك، فالذي يكذب على نفسه ويستجيب إلى كذبه يصل إلى مرحلة لا يميز فيها الحقيقة بداخله، أو حوله، ومن ثم يفقد احترامه لنفسه وللآخرين، وافتقاده للاحترام يُفقدته الحب.

2. **A concealed truth, that's all a lie is. Either by omission or commission we never do more than obscure. The truth stays in the undergrowth, waiting to be discovered**³ (Josephine Hart).

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

الحقيقة المحجوبة ما هي إلا كذبة، إما بال حذف أو الإضافة فنحن نقوم بالإخفاء، وتبقى الحقيقة غير مرئية، في انتظار الظهور إلى أرض الواقع.

3. **Advertising is legalized lying** (H. G. Wells).⁴

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

الإعلان كذب مقنن.

4. **A good lawyer must be a great liar** (Alsafar, 2013, p. 56).

Variant: **A good speaker makes a good liar.**⁵ (German)

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

المحامي الناجح يجب أن يكون كذاباً ماهراً

5. **A good lie finds more believers than a bad truth.**⁶ (German)

Variants: *A lie well told is worth more than a stupid fact*⁷ (Italian); *A well-tinted lie counts as the truth*⁸ (Swedish); *There are such things as false truths and honest lies*⁹ (Gypsy). *On the hook of truth only small carp will bite; in the net of falsehood the big salmon are caught*¹⁰ (Latvian); *A dressed up lie is worth more than a badly told truth*¹¹ (Lebanese). *The coat of truth is often lined with lies*¹² (Norwegian). *Never*

² <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/29218-above-all-don-t-lie-to-yourself-the-man-who-lies>

³ <https://quotefancy.com/quote/1580120/Josephine-Hart-A-concealed-truth-that-s-all-a-lie-is-Either-by-omission-or-commission-we>

⁴ <https://medium.com/@chandlerkaradsheh/all-advertising-is-legalized-lying-b353ac700721>

⁵ <https://www.kalimaquotes.com/quotes/11422/a-good-speaker-makes-a>

⁶ <https://www.idlehearts.com/170351/a-good-lie-finds-more-believers-than-a-bad-truth>

⁷ <https://www.penguinrandomhouse.com/books/175691/the-pope-who-quit-by-jon-m-sweeney/readers-guide/>

⁸ <https://vdoc.pub/documents/peculiar-proverbs-weird-words-of-wisdom-from-around-the-world-1n8chm7vm1cg>

⁹ <https://www.inspirationalstories.com/proverbs/gypsy-there-are-such-things-as-false-truths/>

¹⁰ <https://www.kalimaquotes.com/quotes/26148/on-the-hook-of-truth>

¹¹ https://www.special-dictionary.com/proverbs/source/l/lebanese_proverb/87751.htm

¹² <https://www.greatthoughtstresury.com/author/norwegian-proverbs>

*show the truth naked - just in its shirt*¹³ (Spanish); *An unexciting truth may be eclipsed by a thrilling falsehood*¹⁴ (Aldous Huxley). *Better the comfort of a lie than the absurdity of the truth*¹⁵ (Tanya Huff); *One thing I think, about humans is that we'd rather live in a comfortable lie than in an unpleasant truth*¹⁶ (Adam Snowflake).

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

الكذبة الحسنة تجد من يصدقها أكثر من الحقيقة السيئة.

It may be translated colloquially as follows:

كذب مسوي ولا صدق منعكش.

كذب مسوي، ولا صدق ملخبط.

6. A good man will not lie, although it be for his profit¹⁷ (Cicero)

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

الإنسان الصالح لا يكذب، وحتى وإن كان الكذب سيفيده.

7. A great lie is like a great fish on dry land; it may fret and fling, and make a frightful bother, but it cannot hurt you; you have only to keep still and it will die of itself¹⁸ (George Crabbe).

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

الكذبة الكبيرة مثل السمكة الكبيرة في الأرض الجافة، فقد ينتابها الغيظ وتتحرك هنا وهناك، ويحدث لها قلق رهيب، إلا إنها لا يمكن أن تؤذيك، وما عليك إلا أن تكون هادئاً، وستموت من نفسها.

8. A half-a-truth is better than a whole lie.¹⁹

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

نصف الحقيقة أفضل من الكذب الكامل.

9. A liar is a man who does not know how to deceive.²⁰

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

الكذاب لا يعرف كيف يخدع.

10. A liar is a nuisance to society.²¹

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

الكذاب مصدر إزعاج للمجتمع.

¹³ <https://www.special-dictionary.com/proverbs/keywords/naked/3.htm>

¹⁴ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/218621-an-unexciting-truth-may-be-eclipsed-by-a-thrilling-falsehood>

¹⁵ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/444977-better-the-comfort-of-a-lie-than-the-absurdity-of>

¹⁶ <https://speakingofresearch.com/2014/06/20/unpleasant-truths-vs-comforting-lies/>

¹⁷ <https://www.quotenova.net/authors/cicero/x469pg>

¹⁸ https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/george_crabbe_394490

¹⁹ <https://www.bartleby.com/89/1041.html>

²⁰ <https://www.morefamousquotes.com/topics/he-who-knows-quotes/>

²¹ <https://www.bartleby.com/89/1041.html>

11. A bitter reality of truth can be wisely told in a sweet tale of lullaby²² (Toba Beta).

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

الواقع المر للحقيقة يمكن التعبير عنه بحكاية لطيفة مثل أغاني الأطفال في المهد.

12. A dull speech which is full of truths is much more brilliant than an eloquent speech which is full of lies!²³ (Mehmet Murat ildan).

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

الخطاب الممل المليء بالحقائق أبلغ من الخطاب الفصيح المليء بالأكاذيب.

13. A false report rides post²⁴ (English) (Howell)

Variants of this proverb: *A false report rides fast²⁵; Bad news travels fast²⁶; Ill news comes apace²⁷; Ill news comes too soon²⁸; Ill news comes unsent for²⁹; Ill news flies fast³⁰; Ill news has wings and with the wind doth go³¹; Ill news is winged with fate, and flies apace³²; Ill news travels fast³³; Ill weeds grow fast.³⁴*

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

الكذب ينتشر أسرع من الصدق.

14. A good liar knows that the most efficient lie is always a truth that has had a key piece removed from it (Carlos Ruiz Zafon).³⁵

Variants: *The best lies are always at least partially true³⁶* (Laurell K. Hamilton); *The slickest way in the world to lie is to tell the right amount of truth at the right time--and then shut up* (Robert A. Heinlein).

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

يدرك الكذاب المحترف أن الكذبة البارعة هي حقيقة حُذف منها جزء أساسي.

15. A good portion of speaking will consist in knowing how to lie (Desiderius Erasmus).

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

²² <https://www.quotemaster.org/q365e8b7a25170c1ffcb2d4662f323f1d>

²³ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/7052604-a-dull-speech-which-is-full-of-truths-is-much>

²⁴ https://www.listofproverbs.com/source/c/chinese_proverb/63077.htm

²⁵ <https://firewoodhoardersclub.com/forums/threads/thought-for-the-day.30325/page-140>

²⁶ <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/bad-news-travels-fast>

²⁷ <https://proverbhunter.com/ill-news-comes-apace/>

²⁸ <https://dict.longdo.com/mobile/?mode=pophai&search=Ill%20news%20comes%20too%20soon>

²⁹ https://nanopdf.com/download/the-penguin-dictionary-of-english-proverbs_pdf

³⁰ <https://worldofdictionary.com/dict/english-russian/meaning/ill-news-flies-fast>

³¹ <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/014107688107400204>

³² <https://www.bartleby.com/348/940.html>

³³ <https://vdict.pro/en-en/good+news+travels+fast%7Cgood+news+travel+fast>

³⁴ <https://www.walmart.com/ip/NEO-NBLOND-Flask-Classic-design-Ill-Weeds-Grow-Fast/472098815?wmlspartner=wlp&selectedSellerId=8935>

³⁵ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/639365-a-good-liar-knows-that-the-most-efficient-lie-is>

³⁶ *The best lies are always at least partially true.*

يتعين أن يكون جزء كبير من الخطاب يحمل مداراة.
يتعين أن يكون جزء كبير من الخطاب غير صريح.

16. A half-truth is the most cowardly of lies.

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

نصف الحقيقة من أسوأ أنواع الكذب.
أسوأ كذبة هي نصف الحقيقة.
إخفاء نصف الحقيقة أسوأ أنواع الكذب.

17. A hound will die for you, but never lie to you. And he'll look you straight in the face³⁷ (George R. R. Martin).

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

كلب الصيد يموت من أجلك، ولا يكذب عليك أبداً، ولا يخشى من النظر في وجهك مباشرة.

18. A house built on lies has a weak foundation³⁸ (Brom).

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

البيت القائم على الكذب أساسه واهن.
أو هن البيوت بيت الكذب.

19. A house made of ice in the middle of desert! And that house is the house of lies!³⁹ (Mehmet Murat ildan)

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

البيت المصنوع من جليد في الصحراء هو بيت الكذب!

20. A jest is half a truth⁴⁰ (Yiddish).

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

المزاح أشبه بالكذب.

21. Actions will always tell the truth; even if you master the art of lying⁴¹

Variant of this proverb: Words may lie but actions will always tell the truth.⁴²

Translation: it may be translated idiomatically as follows:

الأفعال أبلغ من الأقوال.
الفعل أصدقُ إنباء من القول.
المرء ليس بصادقٍ في قوله، حتى يؤيدَ قوله بفعاله.
الصادق من يصدق في أفعاله صدقه في أقواله.
أصلك فَعَلِك.
الصدق في أقوالنا أقوى لنا، والكذب في أفعالنا أفعى لنا.

³⁷ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/449001-a-hound-will-die-for-you-but-never-lie-to>

³⁸ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/1141633-a-house-built-on-lies-has-a-weak-foundation>

³⁹ <https://www.quoteslyfe.com/quote/A-house-made-of-ice-in-the-167751>

⁴⁰ https://www.listofproverbs.com/source/y/yiddish_proverb/76470.htm

⁴¹ <http://www.picturequotes.com/words-may-lie-but-actions-will-always-tell-the-truth-quote-2796>

⁴² <https://www.idlehearts.com/736/words-may-lie-but>

22. A liar should have a good memory⁴³

Variants: *Liars need good memories⁴⁴; A liar ought to have a good memory⁴⁵; If you're a liar, then have a good memory⁴⁶; He who has not a good memory should never take upon him the trade of lying⁴⁷ (Montaigne); A good memory is needed once we have lied⁴⁸ (Pierre Corneille); It is not without good reason said, that he who has not a good memory should never take upon him the trade of lying⁴⁹ (Michel de Montaigne).*

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

إن كنت كذوبًا فكن ذكُورًا؛
إنَّ اللّٰهَ لَا يَهْدِي مَنْ هُوَ كَاذِبٌ كَفَّارٌ.
على الكذاب الاحتفاظ بذاكرة جيدة.
ينبغي أن تكون للكذاب ذاكرة جيدة.
من لا يتمتع بذاكرة في غاية القوة فالأفضل له ألا يخاطر بالكذب.

23. A lie begets a lie.⁵⁰

Variants: *One lie begets another⁵¹; One lie makes many⁵²; One seldom meets a lonely lie⁵³; A lie begets a lie till they come to generations; Once committed, the liar has to go on in his course of lying; (One lie leads to another; it is the penalty of his transgression (F. Jacox)); One wrong submitted to, another follows (Portuguese); A lie carries ten others (German); A lie never has enough (German); He who tells a lie must invent twenty more to maintain it (Pope); He who permits himself to tell a lie once, finds it much easier to do it a second and third time, till at length it becomes habitual (Thomas Jefferson); One lie must be thatched with another, or it will soon rain through (John Owen); It seemed there was no end at all to the lies a person could tell, once she got started (Kim Edwards).*

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as part of the Prophet's tradition as follows:

الكذب يهدي إلى الفجور.

⁴³ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/9230037-a-liar-should-have-a-good-memory>

⁴⁴ <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/liars+need+good+memories>

⁴⁵ <https://edumantra.net/proverbs-with-explanation/10-a-liar-ought-to-have-a-good-memory-meaning-in-english/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.idlehearts.com/310613/youre-liar-good-memory>

⁴⁷ <http://www.picturequotes.com/he-who-has-not-a-good-memory-should-never-take-upon-himself-the-trade-of-lying-quote-569947>

⁴⁸ <https://www.quoteslyfe.com/quote/A-good-memory-is-needed-once-we-270365>

⁴⁹ <https://thebombayreview.com/2021/02/08/essay-of-liars-by-michel-de-montaigne-classical-archives/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.hallofpeople.com/en/proverbs.php?id=74>

⁵¹ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/7275741-telling-one-lie-begets-another-lie-that-begets-another-lie>

⁵² <http://www.english-for-students.com/One-Lie-Makes-Many.html>

⁵³ https://www.classicthesaurus.com/one_seldom_meets_a_lonely_lie

24. A lie has speed but truth has endurance (Edgar J. Mohn)

Variants: *My father always told me that what's wrong with lying is that it's an admission of weakness. If you're the strongest, you can afford to tell the truth*⁵⁴ (K. J. Parker); *Truthful lips endure forever, the lying tongue, for only a moment*⁵⁵ (Bible); *A lie is for a while, truth still the Last Day*.⁵⁶

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

دولة الباطل ساعة ودولة الحق إلى قيام الساعة.
جولة الباطل ساعة، وجولة الحق إلى قيام الساعة.

25. A lie though it promises good will do thee harm and truth will do thee good at last.⁵⁷

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

الصدق طمأنينة، والكذب ريبة.

26. All truth is not always to be told⁵⁸

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

ما كل ما يُعلم يقال.
ليس كل ما يُعرف يقال.
لكل مقام مقال.

27. Always tell the truth and you'll never have to remember your words⁵⁹ (Kiki Archer).

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

قل الحق وأجرك على الله.

28. Any lie will find believers, as long as you tell it with force enough⁶⁰

Queen Christina (1933) (Adamson, 2004, 64).

Variants: *A great lie is the best*⁶¹ (German); *If you tell a big enough lie and tell it frequently enough, it will be believed*⁶² (Adolf Hitler).

Translation: it may be translated idiomatically as follows:

كلما كبرت الكذبة، سهل تصديقها.

⁵⁴ http://www.notable-quotes.com/p/parker_k_j.html

⁵⁵ <https://www.esv.org/Proverbs+12/>

⁵⁶ <https://quoteinvestigator.com/2014/07/13/truth/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.bartleby.com/89/1041.html>

⁵⁸ <https://store.line.me/theshop/product/cc2fc864-7778-4cc1-8078-189d20a6c09f/en>

⁵⁹ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/7072343-always-tell-the-truth-and-you-ll-never-have-to-remember>

⁶⁰ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0024481/characters/nm0001256>

⁶¹ <https://www.bartleby.com/89/1041.html>

⁶² <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/553-if-you-tell-a-big-enough-lie-and-tell-it>

29. April Fool's Day⁶³

Variant: April Fools' Day⁶⁴; All Fools' Day.⁶⁵

Translation: it may be translated idiomatically as follows:

كذبة إبريل/ كذبة نيسان

30. Ask no questions and you will be told no lies.⁶⁶

Variants: *Ask me no questions and I'll tell you no lie* (English) (Stone, 2006, 258); *Ask no questions and hear no lies* (American) (Stone, 2006, 258); *Ask me no questions and I'll tell you no fibs.*⁶⁷

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

من سأل عما لا يعنيه، سمع ما لا يرضيه.
يبدأ الكذب حقًا عندما نكون مرغمين على الجواب.
تحاش معي الأسئلة كي لا تجبريني على الكذب.

B. From Arabic into English

31. اجتنب مصاحبة الكذاب فإن اضطررت إليه فلا تُصَدِّقْهُ ولا تعلمه أنك تكذبه فإنه ينتقل عن ودك ولا ينتقل عن طبعه.⁶⁸

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

Avoid the company of a liar; if you can't avoid him, don't believe him.

32. آفة الحديث الكذب.⁶⁹

شر القول الكذب.⁷⁰

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

Lies are the plague of speech.

33. أكذب من سراب⁷¹ / أكذب من مسيلمة (الكذاب)⁷² / أكذب من سجاح⁷³ / أكذب من عرقوب⁷⁴ / أكذب من قبيض القوم⁷⁵ / أكذب من فرس الليل⁷⁶ / أكذب من الريح⁷⁷ / أكذب من فاخنة⁷⁸ / ما أنت إلا فاخنة⁷⁹ / كلامه ريح في قفص⁸⁰ / أكذب من زراق⁸¹ / أكذب من نائحة⁸² / أكذب من عربة⁸³ / حد يقول البغل في الابريق⁸⁴

⁶³ https://www.lexico.com/en/definition/April_Fool's_Day

⁶⁴ https://www.lexico.com/en/definition/April_Fool's_Day

⁶⁵ https://www.lexico.com/en/definition/all_fools'_day

⁶⁶ http://www.lexiconer.com/translate/Ask_no_questions_and_you_will_be_told_no_lies#.YuK8m3ZBzIU

⁶⁷ <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/235456-ask-me-no-questions-and-i-ll-tell-you-no-fibs>

⁶⁸ <https://cutt.us/cJhsS>

⁶⁹ <https://hadith.inoor.ir/fa/hadith/316286/hadith-noorlib?rownumber=NaN>

⁷⁰ <https://library.tebyan.net/fa/Viewer/Text/106223/410>

⁷¹ <https://www.al-jazirah.com/2015/20150314/rj7.htm>

⁷² https://www.albasrah.net/ar_articles_2011/0411/abo3bdala_020411.htm

⁷³ <https://cutt.us/lpdUp>

⁷⁴ <https://cutt.us/JRMel>

⁷⁵ <https://cutt.us/D9CvI>

⁷⁶ <https://ashabakah.com/feeds/web/ar/oped/article/592787>

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:
More fake than a mirage.

34. الصبح نور.

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:
Truth is light.

35. الخرس خير من الكذب.⁸⁵

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:
Silence is better than lying.

36. الصدق زي موسمي ترتديه الأكاذيب⁸⁶ (أنيس منصور).

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:
Truthfulness is a seasonal dress worn by lies.

37. الكذب داء والصدق دواء⁸⁷
الصدق عز والباطل ذل⁸⁸.

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:
Lying is a disease and truth is a cure.

38. الكذب يؤدي إلى النفاق.⁸⁹

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:
Lying leads to hypocrisy.

39. (قال رسول الله – صلى الله عليه وسلم) الكذوب من كذب على يمينه...⁹⁰

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:
A liar is someone who lies in his oath...

40. اللي يسمعك يصدقك⁹¹

أسمع كلامك أصدقك، أشوف أمورك أستغرب/ أستعجب⁹²

Translation: It may be translated literally as follows:

⁷⁷ <https://www.maktabatalfeker.com/book.php?id=5350>

⁷⁸ <https://al-maktaba.org/book/12929/3284>

⁷⁹ <http://islampost.com/l/adb/5444/176.htm>

⁸⁰ <http://islampost.com/k/adb/5444/209.htm>

⁸¹ <http://islampost.com/l/adb/5444/252.htm>

⁸² <https://cutt.us/YhBtX>

⁸³ <https://www.maktabatalfeker.com/book.php?id=5350>

⁸⁴ <https://www.maqola.net/quote/54219/>

⁸⁵ <http://islampost.com/w/amm/Web/4327/10.htm>

⁸⁶ <https://jdohakeem.com/i/68449721>

⁸⁷ <https://cutt.us/iCXEm>

⁸⁸ <https://cutt.us/uSy0e>

⁸⁹ <https://arabicradio.net/news/29692>

⁹⁰ <http://islampost.com/w/krij/Web/4002/245.htm>

⁹¹ <https://www.alriyadh.com/717594>

⁹² <http://www.alwasatnews.com/news/1054483.html>

The one who listens to you believes you.

41. إذا أردت أن تكذب فأبعد شاهدك/شهودك⁹³

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

If you want to lie, be away from your witness.

42. أربعة أذلاء أبدًا: الفقير، والنمّام، والمدان، والكاذب.⁹⁴

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

Four servile people for ever: the poor, the gossip, the guilty and the liar.

43. الحيلة سلاح الكذاب.⁹⁵

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

The trick is the liar's weapon

The trust of the innocent is the liar's most useful tool⁹⁶ (Stephen King)

44. الصمت يثير الشك لكنه أفضل من الكذب⁹⁷

الخرس خير من الكذب.

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

Silence is suspicious but it's better than lying.

45. (قال أبو بكر الصديق – رضي الله عنه) الصدق أمانة والكذب خيانة.⁹⁸

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

Truthfulness is to be honest and lying is betrayal.

46. الكذب فساد كل شيء.⁹⁹

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

Lying ruins everything.

47. الكذب في العاجلة عار، وفي الآجلة نار.¹⁰⁰

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

In the World lying is disgrace, and in the Hereafter it is Fire.

48. الكذاب متهم في قوله، وإن قويت حجته، وصدقت لهجته.¹⁰¹

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

The liar is doubted in his saying even if his argument is convincing and his speech is true.

⁹³ <https://al-maktaba.org/book/10497/304>

⁹⁴ <https://ar.lib.eshia.ir/40869/1/254>

⁹⁵ <https://cutt.us/rfwkF>

⁹⁶ <https://quotefancy.com/quote/759049/Stephen-King-The-trust-of-the-innocent-is-the-liar-s-most-useful-tool>

⁹⁷ <https://cutt.us/7vgnQ>

⁹⁸ <https://cutt.us/uvZcH>

⁹⁹ <https://cutt.us/oi6gX>

¹⁰⁰ <https://forums.alkafeel.net/node/135962>

¹⁰¹ <https://cutt.us/gd9kT>

49. الكذب يوجب الوقعة.¹⁰²

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

Lying drives a wedge between people.¹⁰³

50. الكذب يزري بالإنسان.¹⁰⁴

Translation: It may be translated semantically as follows:

Lying makes man despicable.¹⁰⁵

51. اكذب النفس إذا حدثتها¹⁰⁶ / هواك لم يكذب عليك أمير¹⁰⁷ / إنك إن ملكت هواك لم تعمل إلا بالحق¹⁰⁸ / ومن لم يملك هواه اشتغل بالهذيان.

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

It is better to conquer yourself than to win a thousand battles¹⁰⁹ (Buddha); Rule your mind or it will rule you¹¹⁰ (Horace).

52. الرائد لا يكذب أهله¹¹¹

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

A man is often a bad adviser to himself and a good adviser to another¹¹² (Irish Proverb)

53. إْحْساسِي ما يَكْذِبْش¹¹³ (في قرارة النفس – في الصميم – أحس بذلك في قرارة نفسي)

(Egyptian, colloquial)

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

Feel it in one's bones (to suspect something strongly; have a suspicion that is not based on facts but feelings). *I knew she would marry my son. I felt it in my bones* (El-Batal, 2005, 4).

54. الطمع الكاذب فقر حاضر¹¹⁴

المال مكذوب عليه¹¹⁵

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

¹⁰² <http://www.ahlolbayt.net/old/radhael/alkhathib.htm>

¹⁰³ <https://cutt.us/kKbOU>

¹⁰⁴ <https://cutt.us/yTWaF>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.psychalive.org/compulsive-liars/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://al-maktaba.org/book/33588/855>

¹⁰⁷ <https://al-maktaba.org/book/10497/557>

¹⁰⁸ <https://al-maktaba.org/book/10496/67>

¹⁰⁹ https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/buddha_121206

¹¹⁰ <https://respectyourself.org.uk/rule-mind-will-rule/>

¹¹¹ <http://www.saaid.net/arabic/476.htm>

¹¹² <https://www.kalimaquotes.com/quotes/11897/a-man-is-often-a-bad>

¹¹³ https://www.dodystories.info/2022/03/ankzoni_01259758891.html

¹¹⁴ <http://islamport.com/k/adb/5494/2411.htm>

¹¹⁵ <https://al-maktaba.org/book/10614/312>

The avarice person is ever in want.¹¹⁶ (Horace)

A greedy man is always poor.¹¹⁷

.55 المية تُكذب الغطاس¹¹⁸ (Egyptian, colloquial)

عند الرهان تعرف السوايق¹¹⁹

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

The water gives the lie to the diver.¹²⁰

If someone pretends to be a driver, water will bring out the truth. It can apply to anyone who is boasting.

Put your money where your mouth is.¹²¹

Stop just talking and stake your own money! From gambling, it can also be said to someone giving investment advice; to do something rather than to just talk about it. *You want me to bet on that horse? Did you? Why don't you put your money where your mouth is? If this is such a good stock, you buy it. Put your money where your mouth is!*¹²²

The proof's in the pudding (a popular figure of speech meaning the quality, effectiveness or truth of something can only be judged by putting it into action or to its intended use. For example: *So the proof is in the pudding: they made a big pronouncement on crime prevention, and now they have to follow through.*

.56 أم الكاذب عربة كلما دارت ضرطت¹²³ (وتقول لمن حدّث بالمحال)

أم الكاذب بكر.¹²⁴

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

It is impossible to tie a knot without the thumb.¹²⁵

.57 صبغني فلان¹²⁶

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

I felt cheated.

.58 فلان ينفخ في البوق¹²⁷

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

¹¹⁶ <https://quotefancy.com/quote/830043/Horace-The-avarice-person-is-ever-in-want-let-your-desired-aim-have-a-fixed-limit>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.kalimaquotes.com/quotes/11485/a-greedy-man-is-always>

¹¹⁸ <https://elaph.com/Web/opinion/2012/12/779044.html>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.startimes.com/f.aspx?t=14463951>

¹²⁰ https://arabic.desert-sky.net/coll_proverbs.html

¹²¹ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/to-put-your-money-where-your-mouth-is>

¹²² <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/put+his+money+where+his+mouth+is>

¹²³ <http://islamport.com/l/adb/5444/176.htm>

¹²⁴ <http://islamport.com/l/adb/5444/175.htm>

¹²⁵ <https://www.kalimaquotes.com/quotes/7949/it-is-impossible-to-tie>

¹²⁶ <https://al-maktaba.org/book/33665/1714>

¹²⁷ <https://cutt.us/qglixo>

It is useless to knock at the door of a deaf man¹²⁸ (Greek).

A juicy bone is useless to a dog with no teeth¹²⁹ (African).

59. كَذَابٌ فِي أَصْلٍ وَشُئُهُ¹³⁰ (كَذَابٌ صَفِيْقُ الْوَجْهِ¹³¹)
مِنْ كَذْبِ زَهَبِ مَاءٍ وَجْهَهُ¹³² (لِقْمَانِ الْحَكِيمِ)

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

A barefaced liar (a shameless liar): one who displays no shame about lying even if they are exposed. *She's a barefaced liar; she hadn't asked me for money at all, or else I would have given it to her* (El-Batal, 2005, 90).

60. كَذَابٌ وَيَبِرُّ خَطَأَهُ¹³³

Translation: It may be translated idiomatically as follows:

Every lie is two lies — the lie we tell others and the lie we tell ourselves to justify it¹³⁴ (Robert Brault).

• Conclusions

Proverbs and sayings are an essential part of language. They are needed in everyday life. Hence, they deserve special attention. In the same vein, translating proverbs poses many difficulties for translators. Therefore, they deserve considerable efforts from translators to render suitable meanings. The study proposed a model for translating proverbs and sayings. The model was validated by a group of jurors specializing in translation, curriculum and instruction. Then the model was applied to lying proverbs and sayings. The application came up with three kinds of translations: literal, semantic, idiomatic, and colloquial.

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¹²⁸ <https://www.idlehearts.com/309010/useless-knock-door-deaf-man>

¹²⁹ <https://www.inspirationalstories.com/proverbs/t/african-on-dogs/>

¹³⁰ <https://quizlet.com/196691064/idiom-english-arabic-flash-cards/>

¹³¹ <https://cutt.us/Xj3SR>

¹³² <http://www.alwasat.com.kw/ArticleDetail.aspx?id=77557>

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Appendix 1

Jury Members' Evaluation Sheet

Dear professor,

Name..... Position.....

This model is a part of a study entitled "A Proposed Model for Translating Proverbs: A Case of Lying Proverbs." The study aims at developing a model for translating proverbs and applying it to lying proverbs in English and Arabic. Kindly respond to the following points.

CRITERIA FOR VALIDATING THE MODEL	YES		NO
	To a great extent	To some extent	
1. Is the model suitable for translating proverbs?			
2. Is the model clear?			
3. Is the model comprehensive?			
4. Can the model be applied by different translators consistently?			
5. Does the mode take into account understanding proverbs?			
6. Does the mode take into consideration the origin of proverbs?			
7. Does the model attend to proverb characteristics?			
8. Does the mode pay attention to the different strategies of translating proverbs?			
9. Does the model consider translation as a process?			
10. Does the model take into account translation as a product?			

If there is something else to be added, omitted, modified, from your point of view, would you provide it, please?

- I think the following should be added:

.....
.....
.....
.....

- I think the following should be omitted:

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.....
.....
.....

- I think the following should be modified:

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.....
.....
.....

- Additional comments:

Please add any items and/or comments that you consider important for the model validation.

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